

Research Article

Q-absorbance ratio spectrophotometric method for simultaneous determination of atenolol and ivabradine hydrochloride in synthetic mixture

Pooja A. Patil*, Hasumati A. Raj, Gautam B. Sonara

Department of Quality Assurance, Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College Kim, Surat, Gujarat, India

*For correspondence

Pooja A. Patil,
Post Graduate student,
Department of Quality
Assurance, Shree Dhanvantary
Pharmacy College Kim, Surat,
Gujarat, India.
Email: patilpooja1611@gmail.
com

ABSTRACT

Objective: It describes Simultaneous estimation of simple, accurate, precise, robust and economical Q-Absorbance ratio spectrophotometric method for Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl in synthetic mixture. Objective of the study was to deliver information related to Ivabradine HCl and Atenolol combination's analytical method.

Methods: Absorbance ratio method for the ratio of absorbance at two selected wavelengths, one which is an iso-absorbive point and other being the λ -max of one of the two components. Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl showed an iso-absorbive point at 286.40 nm in methanol. The second wavelength used was 276 nm which is λ_{\max} of Atenolol in methanol. So it was economic in nature. The linearity was obtained in the concentration range of 20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Atenolol and 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Ivabradine HCl. The concentration of the drugs was determined by using ratio of absorbance at iso-absorbive point and at the λ_{\max} of Atenolol.

Results: This method is linear for both drugs; in range 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Ivabradine HCl and 20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Atenolol found at λ_{\max} of Atenolol 276nm ($R^2 = 0.9990$) and at Iso-absorbive point 286.40 nm ($R^2 = 0.9998$). % recovery for Ivabradine HCl found 100.47% and Atenolol 100.32%. And all validation parameter (Robustness, Ruggedness, Interday, Intraday) show %RSD >2%. And Limit of detection for Ivabradine HCl and Atenolol at λ_1 (maximum wavelength) and λ_2 (Iso-absorbive point) was found 0.309 and 0.181 respectively. % Assay for Ivabradine HCl and Atenolol found to be 100.58% and 100.13% respectively.

Conclusions: The method was successfully applied to pharmaceutical synthetic mixture which was considered in approved patent which show no interference. The result of analysis has been validated statistically and by recovery studies. So this method accurate, precise, robust, rugged and economic in nature.

Keywords: Atenolol, Ivabradine HCl, Absorbance ratio method, Iso-absorbive point

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Introduction

Atenolol chemically (RS) - 4 - (2-hydroxy -3-isopropyl amino propoxy) phenyl Acetamide is a β -adrenoreceptor blocker primarily used for hypertension, angina pectoris and myocardial infraction. It mainly acts by inhibition of renin release and angiotensin-II and aldosterone production.¹

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Ivabradine HCl.

Figure 2: Chemical structure of Atenolol.

Ivabradine HCl (S)-3- {3- [(3,4-dimethoxy bicycle [4.2.0] octa-1,3,5-triene-7-ylmethyl) Methyl amino] propyl}-7, 8-dimethoxy-2, 3, 4, 5-tetrahydro-1H-3-benzazepine-2-one is a channel blocker which is present at the sinus node and is responsible for generating the early phase of spontaneous diastolic depolarization in pacemaker cells, thereby reducing the frequency of action potential initiation and increasing the time required to reach the voltage threshold for action potential initiation.² Hence, it improves blood pressure and pain in angina pectoris. Both drugs show a beneficial effect when combined without any adverse effect.³⁻⁶

In this present study, methanol AR grade was used as solvent for Q-Absorbance ratio method for both drugs using UV spectrophotometry. The present method used a cheap solvent. It shows accurate

and precise method, it is economic and reproducible.

Materials and Methods

Instrument

Spectroscopic analysis was carried out on a UV/Visible 2450 and UV/Visible 1800 (Shimadzu) double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer with software of UV Probe version 2.34.

A semi-micro analytical balance (Sartorius CD2250, Germany) was used for weighing purposes.

Material

Analytically pure Ivabradine HCl raw material was received as a gift sample from Torrent Pharmaceutical, Ahmedabad and Atenolol raw material as a gift sample from Meridian Enterprise Pvt. Ltd., Navsari.

Methanol AR Grade (from FINAR Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad), Distilled Water (from SDPC research laboratory, Surat), NaOH AR Grade (from Rankem Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad), HCl AR Grade (from Astron Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad) were used for development purposes.

Methods

Preparation of standard solution

A 10 mg of standard Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl were weighed and transferred to 100 ml separate volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol. The flask was shaken and volumes were made up to mark with methanol to give a solution containing 100 μ g/ml each of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl.

Methodology

Absorbance ratio method uses the ratio of absorbance at two selected wavelengths, one which is an iso-absorptive point and the other being the λ_{max} of one of the two components. From overlay spectra of 2 drugs, it is evident that Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl show an iso-absorptive point at 286.40 nm. The second

wavelength used is 276 nm of λ_{\max} of Atenolol. Working standard solution having concentration 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Atenolol and 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Ivabradine HCl (taken ratio 10:1 Atenolol: Ivabradine HCl according to US patent³) were prepared in methanol and the absorbance at 286.40 nm iso-absorbive point and 276 nm λ_{\max} of Atenolol were measured and absorptivity were calculated using calibration curve.

Figure 3: Overlay spectra of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl in methanol.

The concentration of 2 drugs of mixture in 10:1 ratio at 286.40 nm and 276 nm can be calculated using following equation:⁸

$$C_x = \frac{Q_M - Q_y}{Q_x - Q_y} \times \frac{A_1}{a_{x1}} \quad C_y = \frac{Q_M - Q_x}{Q_y - Q_x} \times \frac{A_1}{a_{y1}}$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 are absorbance of mixture at 276 nm and 286.40 nm; a_{x1} and a_{y1} are absorptivity of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl at 276 nm and a_{x2} and a_{y2} at 286.40 nm respectively.

$$Q_M = A_2 / A_1, \quad Q_X = a_{x2} / a_{x1} \quad \text{and} \quad Q_Y = a_{y2} / a_{y1}.$$

Validation of proposed method

The proposed method was validated according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline.⁴

Linearity

The calibration curve was plotted over a concentration range 20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Atenolol

and 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Ivabradine HCl. Appropriate Aliquots from the standard stock solution of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl were used to prepare 2 different sets of dilution: Series A and B as follow, series A consisted of different concentration of Atenolol (20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Aliquots from stock solution of Atenolol in methanol (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was pipette out in to a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted with methanol to get final concentration 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (2, 4, 6, 8, 10 ml). Series B consisted of different concentration of Ivabradine HCl (2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Aliquots from stock solution of Ivabradine HCl in methanol (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was pipette out in to a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted with methanol to get final concentration 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 ml).

Method precision

The precision of instrument was checked by repeated scanning and measurement of absorbance of solution ($n=6$) 3 concentration (lower, middle, highest) and 3 replicates for Atenolol and Ivabradine mixture without changing the parameter of proposed spectrophotometry method.

The intraday and inter day precision of proposed method was determined by analyzing the corresponding response 3 times on same day on 3 different days of 3 different concentrations (2+20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 6+60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 10+100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The result was reported in terms of relative standard deviation (RSD%).

Accuracy

The accuracy of method was determined by calculating the recoveries of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl by standard spiking method. Known amount of standard solution for Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl were spiked at 80%, 100% and 120% level to pre-quantified sample solution of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl (40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Atenolol and 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Ivabradine HCl). The amount of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl were estimated by applying obtained values to the respective regression line equation.

This recovery study done in synthetic mixture which was made according to US patent⁷ and amount taken equivalent to 10 mg of Ivabradine HCl other side Atenolol directly weighed 100 mg in mixture. Amount taken and study data given in Table 5 and 6.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification

The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantitation (LOQ) of the drug were derived by

Calculating the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) i.e. 3.3 for LOD and 10 for LOQ) using the following equation designated by International conference on Harmonization guidelines.

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma/S, LOQ = 10 \times \sigma/S$$

where, σ = standard deviation response and S = slope of the calibration curve.

Robustness and ruggedness

The sample solution was prepared and then analyzed with change in typical analytical condition like stability of analytical solution.

Analysis of drugs in sample

The absorbance of the sample solution i.e. A1 and A2 were recorded at 276.00 nm (λ_{max} of Atenolol) and 286.40 nm (iso-absorbive point) respectively. Ratio of absorbance were calculated, i.e. A2/A1. Relative concentration of two drugs in the sample was calculated using below equations. The analysis procedure was repeated three times with synthetic mixture.

$$C_y = \frac{Q_M - Q_x}{Q_y - Q_x} \times \frac{A_1}{a_{y1}} \quad C_x = \frac{Q_M - Q_y}{Q_x - Q_y} \times \frac{A_1}{a_{x1}}$$

For synthetic mixture, 400 mg taken in which it equivalent to 10 mg IVA and 100 mg ATN. In 100 ml volumetric flask it was taken and dissolved in 25 ml of Methanol and sonicated for 15 min., made up to 100 ml with Methanol and shake vigorously and filtered it. From it 0.4 ml taken and diluted up to 10 ml of Methanol to make 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ivabradine HCl and 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Atenolol.

Results and Discussion

In absorbance ratio method (Q-analysis), the primary requirement for developing a method for analysis is that the entire spectra should follow the Beer's law at all the wavelength which was fulfilled in case of both these drugs were 276.00 nm (λ_{max} of Atenolol) and 286.40 nm (iso-absorbive point) at which the calibration curve were prepared for both drugs. The overlain UV absorption was found to be simple, accurate, precise, robust, rugged and economic. Hence the method can be employed for the routine analysis of these two drugs in combined form.

Figure 4: Calibration curve of Atenolol (276 nm) and Ivabradine HCl (286.40 nm).

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Atenolol at 286.40 nm.

Conclusions

The proposed spectrophotometric method was to be simple, sensitive, accurate, precise, robust, rugged and economic for determination of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl in synthetic mixture. The method utilizes easily available and cheap solvent for analysis from synthetic mixture. This both drug show more beneficial

Table 1: Regression data of Atenolol (276 nm) and Ivabradine HCl (at 286.40 nm).

At 276.00 nm Conc.(µg/ml)	Absorbance ±SD	%RSD	At Isobestic point 286.40 nm Conc. (µg/ml)	Absorbance ±SD	%RSD
2 : 20	0.075±0.004	0.933	2 : 20	0.036±0.002	0.586
4 : 40	0.171±0.015	0.876	4 : 40	0.068±0.005	0.798
6 : 60	0.281±0.016	0.710	6 : 60	0.101±0.008	0.826
8 : 80	0.398±0.017	0.880	8 : 80	0.135±0.014	0.835
10 : 100	0.506±0.003	0.511	10 : 100	0.169±0.011	0.677

Table 2: Regression data for Atenolol at 286.40 nm.

At Isobestic point 286.40 nm Conc.(µg/ml)	Absorbance ±SD	%RSD
2 : 20	0.036±0.002	0.586
4 : 40	0.068±0.005	0.798
6 : 60	0.101±0.007	0.826
8 : 80	0.135±0.013	0.835
10 : 100	0.169±0.015	0.677

Table 3: Data of precision study for Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl.

Wavelength	Conc.(µg/ml) Ivabradine HCl: Atenolol	Precision			
		Intraday		Interday	
		Mean(n=3)	% RSD	Mean(n=3)	% RSD
286.5 nm	2 : 20 µg/ml	0.126	0.457	0.127	0.453
	6 : 60 µg/ml	0.358	0.161	0.356	0.486
	10 : 100 µg/ml	0.598	0.194	0.595	0.349
276 nm	2 : 20 µg/ml	0.067	0.149	0.067	0.853
	6 : 60 µg/ml	0.195	0.518	0.196	0.590
	10 : 100 µg/ml	0.327	0.466	0.321	0.351

Table 4: Synthetic mixture for Atenolol & Ivabradine HCl in 1:10 ratio as per US Patent.³

Ingredient	Quantity	Use
Ivabradine HCl	100 mg	Antianginal
Atenolol	1000 mg	Antihypertensive
Starch	120 mg	Binder
Magnesium Stearate	40 mg	Lubricant
MCC	1000 mg	Filler
Lactose	1732 mg	Diluent
Hydrophobic colloidal silica	8 mg	Non adherent Agent
Total	4000 mg (4 gm)	

effect in anginal patient compares to monotherapy and its analytical method for combination is not available at any other, so this method is novel for combine form. The common excipient and other additives are usually present

in the synthetic mixture do not interfere in analysis of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl in method, hence it can be conveniently adopted for routine quality control analysis of drug in combined pharmaceutical formulation.

Table 5: Amount weighed for recovery study in synthetic mixture.

Level of recovery	Amt. of Synthetic mixture taken(mg)	Amt. of Drug in synthetic mixture(mg)		Spiked Amt. of API in mixture(mg)		Total Amt. (mg)	
		IVA	ATN	IVA	ATN	IVA	ATN
0%	400	10	100	-	-	10	100
80 %	400	10	100	8	80	18	180
100 %	400	10	100	10	100	20	200
120 %	400	10	100	12	120	22	220

Table 6: Data for recovery study of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl.

Level of recovery	Total Conc. (µg/ml)	Result of recovery study								
		Total Quantity Found (µg/ml)				% Recovery				
	IVA	ATN	IVA	%RSD	ATN	%RSD	IVA	%RSD	ATN	%RSD
0%	4	40	4.02	0.517	40.05	0.062	100.58	0.517	100.13	0.065
80 %	7.2	72	7.21	0.080	72.23	0.211	100.51	0.178	100.72	0.474
100 %	8	80	8.01	0.190	80.10	0.049	100.33	0.380	100.25	0.099
120 %	8.8	88	8.83	0.173	88.10	0.011	100.48	0.319	100.20	0.019
Mean of 3 Determination							100.47	0.348	100.32	0.164

Table 7: Data for LOD and LOQ of Atenolol and Ivabradine HCl (n= 10).

Parameter	IVA	%RSD	ATN	%RSD
LOD (µg/ml)	0.181	0.697	0.309	0.216
LOQ (µg/ml)	0.550		0.938	

Table 8: Data of robustness at λ_{max} and iso-absorbive point.

Condition	Conc. (µg/ml) IVA: ATN	Different Instrument				Different Analyst			
		UV-2450		UV-1800		A		B	
		Mean (n=3)	% RSD	Mean (n=3)	% RSD	Mean (n=3)	% RSD	Mean (n=3)	% RSD
Isobestic point 286.40 nm	4 : 40	0.131	0.431	0.136	0.846	0.131	0.834	0.126	0.836
276.00 nm	4 : 40	0.256	0.676	0.257	0.896	0.256	0.686	0.257	0.896

Table 9: Data of ruggedness at λ_{max} and iso-absorbive point.

Condition	Conc. (µg/ml) IVA: ATN	Different Solvent				Change in Wavelength \pm 0.5 nm			
		2 % water in Methanol		5 % water in Methanol		285.90 nm		289.90 nm	
		Mean (n=3)	% RSD	Mean (n=3)	% RSD	Mean (n=3)	%RSD	Mean (n=3)	% RSD
Isobestic point 286.40 nm	4 : 40	0.213	0.540	0.104	0.553	0.131	0.439	0.084	0.680
276.00 nm	4 : 40	0.236	0.645	0.181	0.956	275.50 nm		276.50 nm	
						0.246	0.473	0.255	0.977

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Table 10: Result of formulation analysis of both drugs.

Drugs	Result of Formulation Analysis (n=3)	
	Conc. of Drug	%Assay
IVA	4 µg/ml	101.13
ATN	40 µg/ml	100.62

Table 11: Validation parameters results of both drugs at 276 nm (λ -max of Atenolol) and at 286.40 nm (iso-absorbative point).

Sr. No.	Parameter	At λ_2 = Isobestic Point (286.40 nm)	At λ_1 = Atenolol (276.00 nm)
1	Wavelength Max.	286.41 nm	276.00 nm
2	Linearity (µg/ml) (n=6)	2-10 µg/ml	20-100 µg/ml
3	Regression equation	$y = 0.0299x + 0.0091$	$y = 0.0058x + 0.0088$
4	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9993	0.9990
5	Accuracy(%Recovery) (n=3)	100.47 ± 0.348	100.32 ± 0.164
6	Precision		
	Intra-day (%RSD) (n=3)	0.161 – 0.457	0.149 – 0.518
	Inter-day (%RSD) (n=3)	0.349 – 0.486	0.351 – 0.853
7	LOD (µg/ml) (n=10)	0.181	0.309
8	LOQ (µg/ml) (n=10)	0.550	0.938
9	Robustness		
	Different Instrument (%RSD) (n=3)	0.431 – 0.846	0.834 – 0.836
	Different Analyst (%RSD) (n=3)	0.676 – 0.896	0.686 – 0.896
10	Ruggedness		
	Different Solvent (%RSD) (n=3)	0.645 - 0.956	0.540 – 0.553
	Change in Wavelength(%RSD) (n=3)	0.439 - 0.680	0.007 – 0.473
11	Assay	100.58%	100.13%

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